

Information Literacy and Knowledge Utilization for National Development: A Case Study of Faculty of Education Lecturers, University of Calabar, Nigeria.

The University Library is established to meet the needs of the University community and the lecturers, in particular. The University lecturers are supposed to acquire information literacy skills which include; the ability to locate, access and recognize their information needs. This will enable them meet up with developments in the global society. This study is conducted to examine the extent of information and knowledge organized by the University library the extent of utilization by the lecturers and the factors affecting proper information and knowledge utilization.